

The fifth power of π : new series representation involving the golden ratio and an application in physics

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Abstract

Although many series exist for π and π^2 , very few are known for higher (and in particular odd) powers of π . In a previous work, we presented series representations for π^3 , in which the golden ratio appears in the prefactor. In this article, we derive, using a trigonometric series obtained by Euler, two representations of π^5 involving infinite sums and the golden ratio. The methodology can be generalized in order to obtain further series, relating by the way π^5 to other mathematical constants. We also mention an intriguing relation, published in 1951 in the journal “Physical Review” (and probably the shortest paper ever published in the journal), pointing out the fact that the ratio of proton to electron masses seems to be very close to $6\pi^5$.

1 Introduction

Many series exist for π and π^2 [1–3]. However, there are only very few published expressions for π^m with $m = 2k + 1$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}^*$. We recently published series representations for π^3 [4], consisting of a prefactor depending only on the golden ratio multiplied by an infinite sum. Besides the understanding of such a scarcity from the mathematical point of view and the derivation of summations in order to point out connections between mathematical constants, π^5 appears in different fields of physics. As an anecdote, it was pointed out by Lenz a long time ago that the quantity $6\pi^2$ is surprisingly very close to the ratio of proton and electron masses. The following series for π^5 is well known:

$$\pi^5 = \frac{1536}{5} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{(2k+1)^5}. \quad (1)$$

A few years ago, Pilehrood and Pilehrood obtained the following Apéry-like series [5]:

$$\pi^5 = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1} 2^{2k+6} (2k+5)!}{(2n-1)^5 \{ [2^{2k+2} (2k^2 + 9k + 6)] + 1 \}} \sum_{j=0}^k \left[-\frac{1}{(2n-1)^2 \pi^2} \right]^j \frac{1}{(2k-2j+1)!}, \quad (2)$$

where $(j, k) \in \mathbb{N}^2$. In 2017, Gupta published new series representations of π , π^3 and π^5 in terms of Euler numbers and π^2 , π^4 and π^6 in terms of Bernoulli numbers [6]. Following his success in discovering a new formula for π , Simon Plouffe [7–9] postulated several identities which relate either π^m or $\zeta(m)$ to three infinite series. Letting

$$S_n(r) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^n (e^{\pi r k} - 1)}, \quad (3)$$

the first three examples are

$$\pi = 72 S_1(1) - 96 S_1(2) + 24 S_1(4), \quad (4)$$

$$\pi^3 = 720 S_3(1) - 900 S_3(2) + 180 S_3(4). \quad (5)$$

and

$$\pi^5 = 7056 S_5(1) - 6993 S_5(2) + 63 S_5(4). \quad (6)$$

In section 2, we obtain series expansions for π^5 using a trigonometric series obtained by differentiation of a relation due to Euler [1] and involving the functions $x \mapsto \cot x$ as well as $x \mapsto \operatorname{cosec} x = 1/\sin x$. We present two of them which are of particular interest since they involve the golden ratio. In section 3, we recall an intriguing connection between π^5 and the ratio of proton and electron masses pointed out by Lenz.

2 New series for π^5 involving the golden ratio

In the book by Borwein and Borwein [1], the following formula, due to Euler

$$\pi^4 \left[\operatorname{cosec}^4(\pi x) - \frac{2}{3} \operatorname{cosec}^2(\pi x) \right] = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(x-n)^4} \quad (7)$$

is presented (13.c, p. 382). Taking the derivative of both sides of Eq. (7) with respect to x yields

$$\pi^5 \cot(\pi x) \operatorname{cosec}^2(\pi x) \left[\operatorname{cosec}^2(\pi x) - \frac{1}{3} \right] = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(x-n)^5}. \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) can be used to derive series expansions for π^5 . In particular, for $x = 1/5$ or $x = 1/10$ for instance, it is possible to obtain expressions of π^5 as series multiplied by a coefficient involving the golden ratio. Indeed, let us consider first the case $x = 1/5$. One has

$$\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{5}\right) = \frac{\phi}{2} \quad (9)$$

and

$$\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{5}\right) = \sqrt{\frac{5 - \sqrt{5}}{8}}, \quad (10)$$

where

$$\phi = \frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2} \quad (11)$$

is the golden ratio. One thus has

$$\cot\left(\frac{\pi}{5}\right) = \frac{\sqrt{2}\phi}{\sqrt{5-\sqrt{5}}} = \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{3-\phi}} \quad (12)$$

and

$$\operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi}{5}\right) = \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{5-\sqrt{5}}} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3-\phi}}. \quad (13)$$

Therefore, using Eq. (8) for $x = 1/5$ yields

$$\pi^5 = \frac{9375}{4} \frac{(3-\phi)^{5/2}}{\phi(\phi+9)} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-5n)^5}. \quad (14)$$

In the same way, setting $x = 1/10$, a similar expansion can be deduced. One has indeed

$$\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{10}\right) = \frac{\sqrt{10+2\sqrt{5}}}{4} = \frac{\sqrt{2+\phi}}{2} \quad (15)$$

and

$$\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{10}\right) = \frac{1}{2\phi}, \quad (16)$$

yielding

$$\cot\left(\frac{\pi}{10}\right) = \phi\sqrt{2+\phi} \quad (17)$$

as well as

$$\operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\pi}{10}\right) = 2\phi \quad (18)$$

giving finally the expansion

$$\pi^5 = \frac{75000}{\phi^3(12\phi^2-1)\sqrt{2+\phi}} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-10n)^5}. \quad (19)$$

Additional expressions can of course be obtained¹ for other values of x , but only a few of them will involve solely the golden ratio. As an example, using $x = \pi/15$, one has

$$\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{15}\right) = \frac{1}{8} \left(\sqrt{30+6\sqrt{5}} + \sqrt{5} - 1 \right) \quad (20)$$

and

$$\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{15}\right) = \frac{1}{16} \left(2\sqrt{3} - 2\sqrt{15} + \sqrt{40+8\sqrt{5}} \right) \quad (21)$$

which unfortunately depends not only on $\sqrt{5}$ (and thus ϕ), but also on $\sqrt{3}$...

¹For instance, using $x = 1/4$, since $\cot(\pi/4) = 1$ and $\operatorname{cosec}(\pi/4) = \sqrt{2}$, one gets $\pi^5 = \frac{1536}{5} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-4n)^5}$.

3 The proton-electron mass ratio

In an article entitled “The Ratio of Proton and Electron Masses”, published by Friedrich Lenz from Düsseldorf (Germany) and received April 5th, 1951 by the Physical Review, the author stated that “The most exact value at present [10] for the ratio of proton to electron mass is 1836.12 ± 0.05 [11]. It may be of interest to note that this number coincides with $6\pi^5 = 1836.12$.” [10]. As mentioned by Dubé [12], Lenz’s note is also probably the shortest article ever published in Physical Review (27 words, 1 number, 1 equation, and 1 reference!). The most exact value at present for the ratio of proton to electron mass is $m_p/m_e=1836.152\ 673\ 89(17)$. Such a number still coincides, although to a lesser extent, to good approximation, with the simple representation $6\pi^5 = 1836.118108711688720$ with 20 significant digits [13]. Such coincidences, however, must be considered with caution [14], keeping in mind the words of George Gamow: “Since the works of Sir Arthur Eddington, it has become customary to discuss from time to time the numerical relations between various fundamental constants of nature. Although until today such discussions have not led to any practical results - that is, to any valuable road signs toward further development of the theory of the still unclear fundamental facts in physics - it may be of some interest to survey the present status of this “clairvoyant” branch of science” [15].

4 Conclusion

We proposed two representations of π^5 involving infinite series and the golden ratio ϕ . There may not be so many series of this kind involving only ϕ (as mentioned in section 2, $\sin(\pi/15)$ contains the irrational number $\sqrt{3}$). The method can be easily applied to derive additional families of series, potentially relating π^5 to other mathematical constants. Moreover, the procedure described here and in Ref. [4] can be easily generalized to obtain series for π^m , $m \geq 6$, either odd or even, by successive derivation of Eq. (8) with respect to x .

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